

THE EFFECTS OF STRATEGIC PLANNING AND GUIDED INSTRUCTION ON SUCCEEDING IN WRITING

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Abstract: Theorists see that there are many ways the teacher can stimulate active participation in writing, in order to develop students' abilities to think, and plan better.

Writing is closely related to thinking, and writing is a way of preparing students to express their opinions in a coherent way.

This research will address how does teaching writing as a process impact on student's performance level at PAAET colleges and institutes In Kuwait?

Keywords: teaching writing, preparing students, PAAET colleges.

1. THE EFFECTS OF STRATEGIC PLANNING AND GUIDED INSTRUCTION IN SUCCEEDING IN WRITING

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Writing is a form of human communication that carries a set of visual signs that constitute a particular language according to agreement and custom, and thus in fact represents the language in its various levels including sentences and different words in addition to the audio clips, as well as a direct representation of thought as it has a set of Jobs of social value.

Writing can also be defined by a system of drawn symbols that can be used to express and convey meaning.

Writing is also a way of making speech visible. There are many functions of writing, such as using them to tell stories and contribute to the wide spread of different news in society. The adoption of different writing systems helps to preserve language and information over time and across countries.

2. WHAT ARE SOME OF THE BENEFITS FROM WRITING SKILL?

Everyone knows that there are skills to learn English, including listening, speaking, reading and writing. When you practice writing on a daily basis for a long time, it will become one of the habits that you will not be able to get rid of, but you will find yourself saving time to write. It will completely reorganize your daily routine in order to provide the right time for writing.

During your journey with writing you will acquire many new terms and words that you use during the blogs that you write and become able to talk and be able to talk on many topics in an attractive manner thanks to the new terms and words you have acquired.

Whether reading books, magazines or various blogs, you will be your source to learn about many written methods. When you start your first steps in writing you will want to learn about the secrets of this world and make friends with people

who share the same interest. It was also the transformation of your entire career to the field of writing articles or writing books and novels when you recognize your writing talent.

3. HOW DO I ACQUIRE AND DEVELOP WRITING SKILLS?

Everyone must believe that writing is an acquired skill; that is, it depends on the person and the extent of self-development, and it applies to all language learning skills in general.

To be able to express yourself clearly, you will need to use effective, powerful and engaging words, but it depends not only on your ability to recognize many words, but also on your ability to use them correctly. You can do this by learning new vocabulary supported by examples of sentences. To illustrate their use, not just memorizing lists of new words without knowing how to use them.

When learning a new word, it is necessary to try to learn all its derivatives, models and placements where the word is usually used (for example, the word "depends" is formulated as follows to depend on, to be dependent) on, a dependent)

You should know how to spell English words and vocabulary correctly, since the misspelling changes the meaning of the sentence altogether.

Knowledge of English grammar is one of the pillars of correct writing, as this can improve the quality of your writing. For example, a simple academic essay consists of several paragraphs (introduction - text - conclusion), and this is the basic structure of the article.

The beginner in the field of writing in English should know the difference between sentence and paragraph:

The sentences in the English language:

They often come from a set of words, and at least one sentence must contain an actor, verb and object, or sentences may be complex.

Write paragraph:

The paragraph in writing is the unity of the subject, and may consist of several other paragraphs linked together to form a single topic.

When writing a paragraph, we need the first sentence to tell us about the subject of the paragraph. The key sentence should be easy, straightforward and short, and the key sentence should talk about only one topic.

The following sentences after the key sentence either explain a rule, give examples, or include a comparison of the subject of the paragraph in the key sentence.

Verb tenses need to be used correctly, pronouns appropriately, and remember to use punctuation because they are the best way to clear and smooth your writing.

You should check the spelling of what has been written at least twice, the first time you look at errors in general, and the second review the errors of the rules.

Writing in English for the first time can be daunting for you, and to avoid being afraid, hold the pen and paper, or sit on your computer;

Be prepared to write in many fields. Be aware that professional writers were not perfect at first, so remember that it is practice that makes professionalism.

First, put some words and thoughts in your mind, and don't forget that you can rewrite what you want to write.

Sometimes writing will flow easily with you, but don't expect that inspiration will always be with you, since you will write spontaneously, so arrange your thoughts with the words you wrote earlier in the paper.

Do not write the subject in Arabic and then try to translate it to English because you will notice after the translation that the sentences will be loose and the composition is strange to English, try to think in English, and write ideas that respond to your mind in the same language.

You can write your daily diary, a few lines of a story you have read, write some e-mails and send them to your friends in English, and the more you keep doing this, the better your writing performance will be.

Some students seem naturally eager to learn and write, but many need and expect their teachers to inspire motivation and challenge.

Among the strategies for motivating students are:

- Love of Matter: Be Passionate.
- Communications area: Get to know your students.
- Independence and Liberation: Give your students.
- some powers in managing the class .
- Personal Learning: Let the students discover for themselves.
- Goals: Do it with students.
- Constructive criticism: Focusing on mistakes, not individuals.
- Instruct: Interested students.

4. LEARNING TO WRITE IN THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE BY LEARNING FROM A COMPUTER (ONLINE LEARNING) IN LIGHT OF THE CORONA 19 PANDEMIC

The Internet is not only a place for chatting, shopping and perusing forums. Universities and colleges of study and educational treatment.

And the use of e-learning in learning and teaching the English language, English language skills and writing skills, which certainly helps it to raise the level of students who suffer from poor English writing.

Create modern studies in old studies or electronic economic studies for writing and other courses to keep pace with modern learning and recent developments in learning technology.

Here are some references that support the discussion on the effects of strategic planning and guided instruction on writing success.

REFERENCES

Books

- [1] Graham, S., & Perin, D. (2007). A Meta-Analysis of the Effectiveness of Writing Instruction: Implications for the Teaching of Writing. In *The Handbook of Writing Research* (pp. 22-36). Guilford Press.
- [2] Rayner, S., & Reid, L. (2016). *Teaching Writing: A Practical Guide for Teachers*. Routledge.
- [3] Kellogg, R. T. (2008). Training Writing Skills: A Cognitive Developmental Perspective. In *The Handbook of Writing Research* (pp. 94-107). Guilford Press.

Articles

- [4] Hyland, K. (2003). *Second Language Writing*. Cambridge University Press.
- [5] Graham, S. (2018). "The Role of Writing in Learning and Literacy Development." *Educational Psychologist*, 53(2), 106-120. doi:10.1080/00461520.2018.1430985

Journals

- [6] Drew, C. (2020). "Teaching Writing in the Digital Age: A Study of Online Instruction in Secondary Education." *Journal of Educational Technology Systems*, 48(3), 285-308. doi:10.1177/0047239518778496

Reports and Guidelines

- [7] National Writing Project. (2012). "Because Writing Matters: Improving Student Writing in Our Schools." Retrieved from National Writing Project
- [8] Graham, S., & Harris, K. R. (2019). "Evidence-Based Practice in Writing Instruction." *The Future of Children*, 29(1), 35-58. doi:10.1353/foc.2019.0001

Online Resources

- [9] Purdue Online Writing Lab (OWL). "Teaching Resources." Retrieved from Purdue OWL
- [10] Edutopia. "Teaching Writing: Strategies for Success." Retrieved from Edutopia